

MEDEMAP

The Media Mapping Blog

Edited by Beata Klimkiewicz

DELIVERABLE 4.1

MeDeMAP - Mapping Media for Future Democracies

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<i>Editor(s)</i>	Beata Klimkiewicz, JU
<i>Author(s)</i>	So far: Renate Schroeder, Director, European Federation of Journalists (EFJ) Beata Klimkiewicz (Jagiellonian University) Jeffrey Wimmer (Charles University) Karolína Šimková (Charles University) Nuno Cintra Torres and Tatiana Chervyakova (Lusófona University) Kirill Filimonov (Charles University)
<i>Reviewer(s)</i>	Individual members of the Steering Committee, according to the topic of the respective blog post
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<i>Status</i>	The blog is open throughout the whole project duration.

<i>Total number of pages (including cover)</i>	5
<i>Dissemination level</i>	Public
<i>Abstract</i>	https://media.medemap.eu/ The blog will offer short posts and texts concerning current problems and developments with regard to media and democracy issues in the EU.

Document History

Version	Date	Submitted by	Changes
V1.0	31/03/2023	P4 - JU	
V2.0	13/06/2024	P4 - JU	New layout

The Media Mapping Blog (medemap.eu)

The Media Mapping Blog

ARCHIVE CONTACT ABOUT

About

The MeDeMAP Media blog is developed under the Horizon Europe project MeDeMAP – Mapping Media for Future Democracies.

The MeDeMAP Media blog focuses on issues that nurture a discussion and exchange of opinions about the role of media in European democracies. The blog explores topics that embrace legal and self-regulatory frameworks for the media, structural development of media systems and its impact on democracy, participation in the media, media trust, expectations of media users, and many others. The blog also aims at creating a vital and moderated space for sharing academic expertise, input from media professionals and activists, policymakers and other actors that facilitate understanding of changing media environments.

We invite interested contributors to offer evidence-based and well-justified texts on topics in focus of our project. We believe that in times of ongoing crisis, amplified by geopolitical, economic and environmental uncertainties, explanatory, deliberative and watchdog roles of the media are more important than ever. So is the academic and analytical debate that sheds light on new conditions in making and opportunities for improvement.

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